

Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocycles. Part-V. Syntheses of *s*-Triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4,]benzothiadiazines, *s*-Triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazines, *s*-Triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline, Imidazo[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole and Benzimidazo[2,1-*b*]benzothiazole as Potential Antimicrobial Agents

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1,2,4-Triazole¹ and tetrahydrobenzothiazole² nucleus are associated with diverse biological properties. In continuation to our earlier work³ we have carried out the syntheses of some heterocyclic compounds where a triazole ring is fused to thiadiazine, dihydrobenzothiadiazine, thiadiazino-quinoxaline ring and benzothiazole ring fused to

imidazole and benzimidazole rings. Thus 5-substituted-4-amino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (1) on reaction with 2-bromo-5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione (6) gave 2, which were neutralised with sodium hydroxide to give 6*H*-7,8-dihydro-7,7-dimethyl-3-substituted-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]benzothiadiazin-9-ol (3) (Scheme 1). The ir and pmr

spectra showed that 3 exist mainly in the enolic form.

7*H*-5,6-Dihydro-3-substituted-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*]-[1,3,4]thiadiazines (4) were synthesised by the condensation of 1 with 1,2-dibromoethane and subsequent neutralisation of the hydrobromide salt with sodium carbonate. Compounds 4 were also synthesised using phase transfer catalysis in comparable yield.

Reaction of 1 ($R = o\text{-Cl-C}_6\text{H}_4$) with 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline in anhydrous ethanol yielded 5*H*-3-*o*-chlorophenyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline (5). 2-Mercapto-4,5-diphenylimidazole and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole when condensed with 6 afforded 6,6-dimethyl-2,3-diphenyl-5,6-dihydroimidazo[2,1-*b*]benzothiazol-8(7*H*)-one (8) and 8,8-dimethyl-7,8-dihydrobenzimidazo[2,1-*b*]benzothiazol-10(9*H*)-one hydrobromide (9) respectively.

Antibacterial activity: All the compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against gram-positive bacteria *Streptococci* and *Staphylococci* and gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas* species applying the agar plate diffusion technique. At 500 ppm concentration, compounds 2f and 3a showed moderate activity (zone of inhibition 9–15 mm) against *Staphylococci* and *Streptococci* whereas 4a and 4c showed activity

against *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas* using chloromycetin as standard drug (17–33 mm). Activities of other compounds were not significant.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal reference, electronic spectra on a Cary 118C spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Perkin-Elmer-Hitachi RMU-6D spectrometer at 70 eV. 5-Alkyl/Aryl-substituted-4-amino-3-mercapto-*s*-triazoles⁴, 2-mercaptobenzimidazole⁵ and 4,5-diphenyl-2-mercaptoimidazole⁶ were prepared following the literature methods.

6*H*-7,8-Dihydro-7,7-dimethyl-3-substituted-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]benzothiadiazin-9-ol (3a; $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$): A mixture of 1 ($R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; 1.92 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-bromo-5,5-dimethylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (6; 2.19 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h. The solvent was then concentrated under reduced pressure and the resulting hydrobromide salt was crystallised from ethanol, 2a, m.p. 245° (Found: S, 7.87. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{SOBr}$ requires: S, 8.13%). The hydrobromide salt was dissolved in 5% NaOH and then acidified with dilute HCl to liberate the free base. It was

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) 2-Bromo-5,5-dimethylcyclohexan-1,3-dione, (ii) NaOH, (iii) 1,2-dibromoethane, (iv) 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline, (v) 2-mercapto-4,5-diphenylimidazole, (vi) Na_2CO_3 and (vii) 2-mercaptobenzimidazole.

crystallised from DMF: 3a (2.18 g, 70%), m.p. 240° (Found: C, 61.09; H, 4.98; N, 17.63. $C_{16}H_{16}N_4SO$ requires: C, 61.54; H, 5.13; N, 17.95%); λ_{max} 262 (ϵ , 21 406) and 400 (ϵ , 3 437); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 (OH), 2 941 (C—H), 1 613, 1 570 (C=C, C=N), 1 361 (CH_3 deformation), 1 099 (C—O), 763, 709 (monosubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.06 (6H, s, $2 \times CH_3$), 2.13 (2H, s, C_6-CH_3), 2.2 (2H, s, C_8-CH_2) and 7.5–8.23 (5H, m, Ar—H); m/z (relative abundance) M^+ 312 (33.6), 280 (14), 177 (53.8), 118 (28.5), 104 (71.7), 103 (97.6), 91 (28.5), 83 (59.1), 80 (20.7), 77 (100), 76 (61.1), 75 (19.1), 71 (18.3), 70 (31.1), 67 (21), 65 (22.2), 54 (30.5) and 51 (13.2); 2b (R=H; 1.33 g, 42%), m.p. 250°d (Found: S, 9.88. $C_{10}H_{10}N_4SBrO$ requires: S, 10.09%); 2c (R=CH₃; 2.21 g, 67%), m.p. 248°d (Found: S, 9.52. $C_{11}H_{15}N_4SOBr$ requires: S 9.67%); λ_{max} 232 (ϵ , 12 375) and 350 (ϵ , 3 125); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 333 (OH), 2 941, 2 817 (C—H), 1 626, 1 575 (C=C, C=N), 1 399, 1 370 (CH_3 deformation), 1 064, 1 013 (C—O); 2d (R=C₂H₅; 1.89 g, 55%), m.p. 195° (Found: S, 9.13. $C_{12}H_{17}N_4SOBr$ requires: S, 9.27%); 2e (R=C₃H₇; 1.86 g), m.p. 260°d (Found: S, 8.48. $C_{13}H_{19}N_4SOBr$ requires: S, 8.91%); 2f (R=*o*-HO—C₆H₄; 2.6 g, 63.4%), m.p. 241° (Found: S, 7.67. $C_{16}H_{17}N_4SO_2Br$ requires: S, 7.82%); 2g (R=*o*-Cl—C₆H₄; 2.48 g, 58%), m.p. 246°d (Found: S, 7.19. $C_{16}H_{16}N_4SOBrCl$ requires: S, 7.48%).

5,6-Dihydro-3-phenyl-7H-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazine (4a; R=C₆H₅). Method (a): A mixture of 1 (1.92 g, 0.01 mol) and 1,2-dibromoethane (1.88 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 6–7 h. The solvent was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue crystallised from ethanol-ether to afford the hydrobromide salt. The hydrobromide salt was dissolved in DMSO and made alkaline with 10% Na₂CO₃ solution to yield the product (0.98 g, 45%), m.p. 238–40° (aq. DMF) (Found: C, 54.87, H, 4.55; N, 25.43. $C_{16}H_{10}N_4S$ requires: C, 55.04, H, 4.59; N, 25.68%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 308 (N—H), 3 170 (C—H), 1 633 (C=N), 768 and 692 cm^{-1} (monosubstituted benzene ring); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.55 (2H, s, S—CH₂), 6.12 (2H, s, N—CH₂) and 7.5–8.0 (5H, m, ArH); 4b (R=*o*-HO—C₆H₄; 1.42 g, 61%), m.p. 246–47°d (Found: S, 13.43. $C_{10}H_{10}N_4SO$ requires: S, 13.7%); 4c (R=CH₃, hydrobromide salt; 1.2 g, 50.6%), m.p. 190° (ethanol-ether) (Found: S, 13.23. $C_8H_9N_4SBr$ requires: S, 13.50%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 290, 3 205 (=NH), 1 618 (C=N) and 1 377 (CH_3) cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.58 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.55 (2H, s, S—CH₂) and 6.38 (2H, s, N—CH₂); 4d (R=C₆H₅, hydrobromide salt; 1.38 g, 55%), m.p. 195°d (Found: S, 12.62. $C_8H_{11}N_4SBr$ requires: S, 12.75%).

Method (b): 1,2-Dibromoethane (1.81 g, 0.01 mol) in chloroform (20 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution containing 1 (R=C₆H₅, 1.92 g, 0.01 mol), water (20 ml), NaOH (0.4 g) and a pinch of benzyltriethylammonium bromide. The mixture was

stirred at 40–50° for 2 h and then at room temperature for 1 h. The semisolid separated was washed with water and then triturated with ethanol to give a white solid, which was crystallised from DMSO-ethanol, (56%), m.p. 240°. The m.m.p. with the compound obtained in method (a) remained undepressed and the ir and pmr spectra were superimposable. Similarly 4 (R=*o*-Cl—C₆H₄) was prepared (53%), m.p. 153–55° (Found: S, 12.22. $C_{10}H_9N_4SCl$ requires: S 12.6%).

5H-3-*o*-Chlorophenyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazino-[5,6-b]quinoxaline (5): A mixture of the triazole (1; R=*o*-Cl—C₆H₄; 2.26 g, 0.01 mol), 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (1.99 g, 0.01 mol) and anhydrous ethanol (35 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for ~6 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the light yellow coloured solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (1.86 g, 53%), m.p. > 270° (Found: S, 7.18. $C_{16}H_{10}N_6S_2ClBr$ requires: S, 7.38%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 040, 1 625 and 1 540 cm^{-1} .

6,6-Dimethyl-2,3-diphenyl-5,6-dihydroimidazo[2,1-b]benzothiazol-8(7H)-one (8): A mixture of 6 (2.19 g, 0.01 mol), 2-mercapto-4,5-diphenylimidazole (2.52 g, 0.01 mol) and anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 7 h. The solvent was then removed and the hydrobromide salt thus obtained was dissolved in DMF and then made alkaline with sodium carbonate solution to yield the product (1.0 g, 54%), m.p. 229° (aqueous acetic acid) (Found: C, 73.94; H, 5.03; S, 8.19. $C_{23}H_{20}N_2SO$ requires: C, 74.19; H, 5.37; S, 8.06%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 695, 1 684 (C=O), 1 590 (C=C, C=N), 1 377 (CH_3), 765 and 697 cm^{-1} (monosubstituted benzene ring); δ (DMSO- d_6) 0.9 (6H, s, $2 \times CH_3$), 2.08 (4H, s, C_6, C_7-CH_2) 7.0–7.4 (10H, m, ArH).

8,8-Dimethyl-7,8-dihydrobenzimidazo[2,1-b]benzothiazol-10(9H)-one hydrobromide (9): An equimolar mixture of 6 and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole in anhydrous ethanol was reacted as described in preparation of 8: the hydrobromide salt (2.1 g, 62%), m.p. 210–212° (char) (Found: C, 50.97; H, 4.32; N, 7.68. $C_{15}H_{15}N_2SOBr$ requires: C, 51.28; H, 4.27; N, 7.97%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 678 (C=O), 1 615, 1 605 (C=C, C=N), 1 376 (CH_3) and 757 (*o*-substituted benzene ring).

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